

PHILOLOGY AND FOREIGN LANGUAGES
THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT READING IN IMPROVING YOUNG
LEARNERS SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: *This article writes about the role of independent reading in teaching speaking skills. Some ways of implementing texts for independent reading are suggested in the following article.*

Key words: *activities, self study, independent learning, young learners, Samantha Stinchcomb, ICT*

Speaking skills is considered one of the major parts of language and require a lot of effort to acquire. Activities which are designed to teach speaking can as well encourage children to become better readers and writers. Motivating pupils to have independent reading and to talk about books can deepen a child's understanding of a text and various verbal activities will encourage children to widen their vocabulary and organize their thoughts which in turn feed into their writing. Speaking and listening are not formally tested or taught for most exams; however, school teachers can help their pupils reach their full literacy potential by encouraging some activities at home. Today the aim of teaching foreign language is build on self studies as working independently help learners to widen their outlook and enhance their critical thinking and confidence. Teachers should encourage learners, especially young learners to work independently by giving different activities to do at home. Meanwhile, not every student has target language atmosphere at home to get assisted, so —they are lost with native tongue when there isn't any target language atmosphere. To avoid such challenges, teacher should get students well prepared during the class; the first and the most essential factor of giving self studies for the young learners is clear instruction.

At the early stage of child's life, nourishing good listening skills is very important. As younger children find it difficult to concentrate for sustained amounts of time, your speech needs to be short, informative and fun. As well as, the tasks you give as homework should be both funny and not energy consuming. Since the child can't concentrate on one subject for a long time the teacher needs to choose tasks carefully for the child to do it independently without any assist. To

get a child to work independently helps him to think critically; furthermore it gives the chance of discovering his own uniqueness.

These activities will help them to increase their ability to learn independently. Reading short stories try to give interesting short stories which are perhaps more challenging than one they would be able to read to you. Ask them to read the details of the story carefully. Once they come to the lesson, ask them to retell the story to you, in their own words. Retrieve information this is basically pulling information out of the text. For example: you might ask a child to tell you what three naughty things Goldilocks did (eating the bears' porridge, sitting in their chairs and sleeping in their beds). Practice inference this is sometimes referred to as 'reading between the lines' and usually involves trying to work out how a character is feeling by the way they are acting. For example: you may say to them: 'Goldilocks ran very fast from the bears' house. Why do you think she did this?' Hopefully your child will have been able to infer from the text that Goldilocks was terrified of the bears! You could extend this by saying: 'Why was she terrified of them?' Your child would then need to think about the fact that Goldilocks had behaved badly in the bears' house and angered them, so she might be afraid of the consequences. Character inference another good activity that involves plenty of inference practice is to ask your child to become a character from the story and conduct an interview with them, asking questions which your child must answer as the character. This will really help consolidate their listening and speaking skills, as well as being a fun activity they will enjoy.

Expand vocabulary show your pupils a picture from the book they have read. Ask them to think of five good adjectives to say out loud to describe a character, object or setting in the picture. Construct some connective chains if you think your child needs help understanding and using connectives, a good game to play is one where you say half a sentence with a connective, such as 'I really wanted to get a dog, however...' and then encourage your child to finish the sentence verbally. Encourage them to finish the sentence in as many ways as possible. Super-charge adjectives and adverbs To help your child expand their vocabulary, find various pictures from books and magazines. Ask them to describe the picture using the best five adjectives they can think of. If there is any movement in the picture, could they use a powerful verb to describe it? Could they add an adverb to this? See if they can plan a story (in writing) centered on this picture, and then present the story verbally to you. Discuss current events look at non-fiction texts and talk about the way they are laid out. For example: look at a newspaper article and ask your child if they can name any of the features of the text (headline, picture,

caption, paragraph, quotations). Ask them to read through the newspaper article and then see if they can sum up verbally what it was about. Start a debate. Debates are an excellent way of ensuring that children are not only finding their voice through sharing opinions and facts, but also find their ears too by patiently listening and respecting the views of others. Suggest a topic your child has expressed an opinion about and get them debating at home. It's a great way of getting the whole family involved and will certainly improve your child's confidence in their communication skills. You never know, you might find you have a budding politician sitting at your dinner table! It may be a good idea to start them off on a subject, for example: discussing whether technology is good for children, or whether the lottery is a good idea. Encourage them to say what they think and back up their opinion with plenty of examples. (This activity will help them if they have to write an argument text as part of the Year 6 English curriculum.)

Be persuasive for another challenging exercise, ask your child to find an item in the house that they must try to sell to you. Encourage them to look at adverts, highlighting persuasive words and phrases that they can use. They then need to write a pitch and attempt to memorize it! Get them to present their pitch to you and then ask them plenty of questions which they need to think up answers to, convincing you that their product is the best. If you have other children, you could ask them to be rival salespeople! This fun and lively activity could even help them practice their ICT skills if they wanted to do a presentation to support their pitch. These are very good methods to teach children increase speaking skills through reading activities. To incorporate self studying into young learners life, the teacher should have following tools on hand: Well designed tasks for each story they help the teachers to assist students' work easily and let your children have choice. We make our children get concentrated on reading as long as they are interested in them, so allowing them to choose the texts to read is the best way to encourage them to read. Host a reading-related event. According to Samantha Stinchcomb, asking students to keep track of what and how much they have read help the teachers be aware of the progress that students make. Lead by example. Your students may as well be well prepared with the help of your sharing your thoughts on the book you and your students are reading and modeling any close reading.

USED LITERATURE:

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